

On The Question of Human Resources Management in the Organization

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Annotation

This article discusses the features of human resource management. Today, this issue has received particular relevance, since all large domestic organizations often use outdated methods of personnel management, and the human resources themselves are considered nothing more than a tool to achieve the set goal of the enterprise. The authors updated the concept of "human potential", in which the psychological component of this definition was highlighted, and the features of human potential management at an enterprise were considered, depending on the influence of 4 groups of external factors.

Keywords: Human resource management, personnel, labor organization, resources, organization strategy

INTRODUCTION

The issue of effective human resource management remains the most important issue for any organization, including educational [1].

This direction, to the same extent as the management of financial and material resources, is essential for every organization, since the development of the organization and its competitiveness depend on the quality of labor resources and the ability to manage them. This explains the relevance of the study of this issue.

One of the first scientists whose studies were devoted to this problem were the scientists of the Michigan School (1984), who argued that human resource management and the very structure of the organization should be regulated in accordance with the strategy of the organization [2].

In accordance with this, they have allocated 4 functions:

- selection;
- certification;
- remuneration;
- development.

In addition, a huge contribution to this process was made by the researchers of the Harvard school - M. Beer et al. (1984), the scheme developed by them is called "Harvard" [1].

The rationale is that human resource management is characterized by two factors:

- 1) the middle manager is responsible for everything;
- 2) employees themselves develop rules that determine the development of personnel.

In modern Russian practice, personnel management is still conservative in nature, and is based on the strict implementation of the assigned tasks by the personnel.

PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

The purpose of this study is to highlight the features of the organization of labor and human resource management in the organization.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve a number of tasks:

- consider the concept of "human resources" and supplement it;
- to highlight the features of the organization of labor and human resource management at the enterprise.

METHODOLOGY

When analyzing the concept, theoretical research methods are used, such as: comparative analysis, synthesis, generalization, study and analysis of various literature on a given problem.

Econometric methods were also used: construction of multiple regression, followed by interpretation of the data obtained.

RESULTS

In modern literature, you can find various definitions of the concept of "human resources", which are presented by both foreign and domestic authors.

Table 1 presents the definitions of the concept of "human resources" [3].

Table 1 - Definitions of the concept of "human resources"

Author	Definition
Russian authors	
Kibanov A.Y.	«This is a concept that reflects the main wealth of any society, the prosperity of which is possible if conditions are created for the reproduction, development and use of this resource, taking into account the interests of each person»
Maksimtsev I.A., Gorelov N.A.	«This is an able-bodied population, which is the material basis of human potential, which characterizes the degree of development of a person's physical and spiritual abilities»
Naumova E.Y.	«This is a collection of people, their physical and mental abilities, which can potentially be used as a production resource, to increase the efficiency of the functioning of any economic system»
Foreign authors	
Armstrong M.	«These are the most valuable assets of an organization and contribute individually and collectively to the achievement of organizational goals»

A source: [3]

Analyzing the above concepts, we can conclude that all authors consider human resources from the perspective of labor resources for an organization.

In our opinion, there is no psychological component of this definition.

The authors propose the following addition to this concept: human resources is a broad concept that includes mental, psychological, social and physical components that directly affect the production process and determine the further state of the organization.

The human resource management system is constantly influenced by a number of factors, such as:

- stage of the life cycle of the organization;
- resource endowment;
- the dynamism of the external environment;
- the degree of competition in the market.

Table 2 describes in detail the features of human resource management, in the conditions of the listed environmental factors.

Table 2 - Features of human resource management under the influence of environmental factors

Factors	Peculiarities
1	2
Resource endowment	An excess of resources (material / labor / financial) leads to their irrational use and, as a consequence, to a decrease in work efficiency. But the lack of resources also has its negative sides: excessive savings on personnel, which subsequently leads to the occurrence of defects and a decline in the quality of production. It is also important to note that working in conditions of constant stress and stress also leads to negative economic consequences.
The dynamism of the external environment	Most often this applies to those industries where frequent changes occur, for example, in the field of high technologies. Here it is necessary to build such a human resource management system that would facilitate adequate assessment, recruitment strategies, training and incentives, in order to facilitate their adaptation to constant changes and stimulate them to learn
Degree of Competition in the	Market If there are several strong competitors in the market, the environment is considered complex enough to function. It is important for the human resources department to constantly monitor the levels of remuneration and methods of incentives, so that other organizations do not contribute to the formation of the turnover of experienced and professional personnel.
Stages of the life cycle of an organization, among which are:	
Organization formation	На данном этапе не выделяют управление человеческими ресурсами как отдельную функцию. Основная функция управления человеческими ресурсами – стабилизация деятельности предприятия
Intensive growth	An independent function is already distinguished here - human resource management. The main task of this direction is to ensure the growth of the company, due to the

	qualitative growth of human potential. It is important for this stage: to develop line managers in relation to competent and modern personnel management
Stabilization	Human resource management activities are carried out in all directions. The main task is to increase the efficiency of enterprise processes, develop and train employees of the enterprise, revise and improve the motivation system for further growth in labor productivity
Crisis	The search and selection of active top managers, the transition to innovations, experimental forms of organizing the interaction of employees and departments are important here. Possibly staff cuts

Source: compiled by the author

Thus, based on the data presented in Table 2, we can conclude that external factors have a special influence on the human resource management system, depending on which the approach to personnel will change.

Further, the risks associated with environmental factors are the most significant for companies in terms of damage and necessitate the formation of an efficient personnel management system of the enterprise.

To determine the range of possible reasons for the implementation of personnel risks, researchers employed in this area resort to building effective mathematical models that allow to qualitatively formalize the task of assessing the personnel management system.

Formalization of the task of assessing the personnel management system at the enterprise is carried out by building a multiple regression model with the following factors, presumably affecting the quality of work, characterized by satisfaction with the provided working conditions:

- employee motivation system;
- average monthly salary of an employee;
- the professionalism of the staff;
- seniority of the employee.

Let y be an indicator of the quality of labor; x_1 - employee motivation system; x_2 is the average monthly salary of an employee; x_3 - staff professionalism; x_4 is the employee's length of service, n is the number of surveyed employees.

Indicators are evaluated in points on a scale from 0 to 1.

Table 3 presents the initial data for constructing a multiple regression model of the dependence of the indicator of personnel satisfaction with the provided working conditions on the assumed factors.

Table 3 - Initial data

Motivation system, x_1 , point	Average monthly salary of an employee, x_2 , point	Professionalism of the staff, x_3 , point	Work experience of the employee, x_4 , point	Quality of work, y , point
0,947	0,829	0,375	0,176	0,491
0,902	0,492	0,448	0,368	0,511
0,512	0,131	0,673	0,676	0,565
0,907	0,439	0,128	0,353	0,358
0,370	0,851	0,310	0,876	0,538
0,631	0,645	0,878	0,227	0,645
0,340	0,169	0,677	0,550	0,514
0,749	0,736	0,853	0,539	0,743
0,192	0,815	0,645	0,878	0,651
0,590	0,997	0,538	0,383	0,579
0,106	0,753	0,266	0,182	0,293
0,282	0,768	0,387	0,410	0,433
0,026	0,087	0,886	0,725	0,583
0,948	0,802	0,114	0,783	0,518
0,126	0,329	0,841	0,526	0,569
0,170	0,798	0,772	0,238	0,548
0,825	0,165	0,071	0,489	0,311
0,577	0,047	0,609	0,600	0,516
0,294	0,171	0,469	0,132	0,314
0,371	0,302	0,553	0,715	0,523
0,673	0,382	0,959	0,403	0,691
0,651	0,347	0,015	0,179	0,211

Further, based on econometric calculations using MS Excel, we obtained the following data, presented in Figure 1.

Регрессионная статистика						
Множественный R		0,900				
R-квадрат		0,810				
Нормированный R-квадрат		0,658				
Стандартная ошибка		0,109				
Наблюдения		22				
Дисперсионный анализ						
	df	SS	MS	F	Значимость F	
Регрессия	4	0,447	0,112	2,598	1,964	
Остаток	17	7,310	4,299			
Итого	21	0,447				
	Коэффициент	Стандартная ошибка	t-статистика	P-Значение	Нижние 95%	Верхние 95%
Y-пересечение	-1,388	5,080	-2,734	0,014	-2,459	-3,167
Переменная X 1	0,166	5,660	2,933	6,242	0,166	0,166
Переменная X 2	0,152	4,490	3,386	5,417	0,152	0,152
Переменная X 3	0,442	6,710	6,601	6,393	0,442	0,442
Переменная X 4	0,240	4,420	5,436	1,737	0,240	0,240

Figure 1 - Results of the "Regression" function implementation

The index of multiple correlation (multiple R), which characterizes the closeness of the relationship between the set of factors under consideration and the trait under study, was 0.90, which indicates the reliability of the model.

Thus, the calculated coefficient of determination suggests that 90% of the variation of the Y feature is taken into account in the model and is due to the influence of the factors included in the model on it. Other factors not included in the model, respectively, account for 10% of the total variation in Y.

Having checked the significance of the obtained equation with the help of Fisher's criterion, one can draw a conclusion about its significance.

In addition, it is important to note that the analysis of the significance of the factors according to the Student's t-criterion also indicated the significance of each parameter for the equation.

The dependence constructed in the course of regression analysis has the following form (1):

$$"y = -1.388 + 0.166 "x" _ "1" " + 0.152 "x" _ "2" " + 0.442 "x" _ "3" " + 0.240 "x" _ "4". (1)$$

Based on the results of the regression analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- if the indicator of the motivation system increases by 1 unit, then the quality of labor will increase by 0.166 units;
- if the level of the average monthly wage increases by 1 unit, then the quality of labor will increase by 0.152 units;
- if the level of professionalism increases by 1 unit, then the quality of labor will increase by 0.442 units;
- if the indicator of the employee's seniority increases by 1 unit, then the quality of labor will increase by 0.240 units.

Thus, according to the results of the conducted regression analysis, it was revealed that the level of their professionalism has the greatest influence on the quality of employees' work.

Therefore, when building an effective personnel management system at an enterprise, it is necessary to pay special attention to this fact.

For these purposes, it is necessary to qualitatively approach the issue of personnel selection, as well as to conduct annual periodic certification and advanced training of personnel.

An indicator such as the level of the average monthly salary of an employee has a lesser impact on the quality of work. However, this does not mean that the level of remuneration does not affect the quality of work and that all employees work equally well or badly, regardless of the level of their remuneration. It is necessary to think about increasing its significance of the factor by bringing the salaries of employees to the ratio "labor price - labor quality".

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- analysis of the definition of "human resources" made it possible to reveal the absence of a psychological component in the definition of this concept, and thus, the author proposed an amended and refined definition of the concept of "human resources";

- during the study of the theoretical aspects of human resource management, 4 groups of factors were identified that affect human resource management, defining their own tasks and management goals, in accordance with the content of each stage;

- on the basis of regression analysis, the factors that most affect the personnel management system were identified, in addition, general recommendations were given for building this system.

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